

Speaking Nature: Strategies for Generating Credible Utterances of Nature Elements or Phenomena

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Abstract

Since sound film was introduced around the 20's decade it has become a fundamental element to transmit information to the audience. The sound design process has come a long way and have reached a point where it is considered a complex task that implies different fields of knowledge such as the technical, the artistic, the psychological, the physical, etc.

Sound designers, DSP Engineers, musicians, etc., design and make use of several tools that allow them to create a given sound scenario not inly for film, but also for TV, Video-Games, Art Installations, media, etc. These sound scenarios can be a recreation of a real sound space or can be the representation of the idea of how a sound space or an element in it could sound.

This thesis explores voice synthesis techniques from sounds of nature and voice recordings as a mean to create credible utterances that preserve the characteristics of the sound of nature while maintaining the intelligibility of the message. We also explore timbre descriptors and the phonetic transcription of the chosen sentences to characterize the sounds of nature and voice sounds in order to generate the utterances automatically.

Desde que el cine sonoro fue presentado alrededor de la década de 1920, este se ha convertido en un elemento fundamental para transmitir información a la audiencia. El proceso de diseño sonoro ha recorrido un largo camino y ha llegado a un punto en el cual se considera una tarea compleja que comprende diferentes campos del conocimiento como lo son el técnico, el artístico, el psicológico, el físico, etc.

Diseñadores sonoros, Ingenieros DSP, músicos, etc., diseñan y hacen uso de varias herramientas que les permiten crear un determinado escenario sonoro no solo en cine, sino también en televisión, videojuegos, instalaciones artísticas, media, etc. Estos escenarios pueden ser una recreación de un espacio sonoro real o puede ser la representación de una idea sobre como un espacio sonoro o un elemento que lo componga podría sonar.

Esta tesis explora técnicas de síntesis de voz a partir de sonidos de la naturaleza y grabaciones de voz con el fin de generar expresiones creíbles que preserven las características del sonido de la naturaleza mientras conservan la inteligibilidad del mensaje. También exploramos descriptores de timbre y la transcripción fonética de las oraciones escogidas para caracterizar los sonidos de la naturaleza y la voz con el objetivo de generar dichas expresiones de forma automática.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The growing interest in the role of sound in movies, video games and media has led to an increase in the development of new technologies and the exploration of different fields in order to create or recreate “real” and/or credible sound spaces. The process of creating a sound space is called sound design. Fields such as human perception, audio signal processing, etc., are fundamental for understanding, creating and implementing the sound design for a given media.

A sound design process could involve many elements, and it goes from recreating footsteps as part of the foley process to creating voices for “non-human” characters, for example; creating robot voices, as Ben Burtt did for the movie WALL-E¹. In the end, the goal is to build a believable sound space.

In the wide world of sounds used to create a sound space there is one very important and commonly used category: Sounds of nature.

The idea of sounds of nature in the sound design process has been addressed mainly from the soundscape perspective, but also sounds of nature have been recorded and transformed in several different ways to enrich movie scenes, video games, art installations, theme parks 4D experiences, music, etc.

This project explores methods for voice synthesis from sounds of nature and voice recordings, as a mean to create credible utterances that preserve the characteristics of the nature sound or phenomena while maintaining the intelligibility of the message.

Motivation

Sounds of nature are present in every day life and they give us constant information on the actual state of our planet, however we don't always know how to interpret or understand what message is being transmitted by nature.

This project explores the behavior and main characteristics sounds of nature and propose methods to answer to the research question: If it could, how would nature speak?

We'll explore fields such as audio signal processing, human perception, recording techniques, etc, to propose voice synthesis methods to create credible utterances from sounds of nature and voice recordings.

Goals

- Research on speech processing techniques and digital audio effects related to voice synthesis.
- Explore different voice and sounds of nature recording methods.
- Define the best method/s to perform voice synthesis from sounds of nature and voice recordings.
- Generate a set of credible utterances from sounds of nature and voice recordings.

¹<http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eySh8FOUphM>

2. STATE OF THE ART

2.1 Sound Design

Sound design involves a complex process in which many tools are applied as a means to generate a given sound scenario. Its complexity relies on the need of the sound designer to understand and master fields such as technology, human perception, aesthetics and semiotics [1]. Andy Farnell describes the sound design process as a structure supported by three pillars of knowledge, these are: Physical, mathematical and psychological [2], this indicates that the sound design process needs to take into consideration how the recording and audio signal processing techniques applied to a sound will affect our perception of it and will evoke emotions related to the sound event, but also to understand what are the physical properties of a sound in order to build it.

2.1.1 History of sound design

Sound design has been present in human history since ancient times[3], it is believed that before musical instruments existed, our ancestors used noise devices to scare evil spirits [2]. In theater, music and sound effects were played and recreated in real time. In films, music was first used for two reasons: to drown the noise of projectors and to give an emotional atmosphere [4], and as recording and playback technologies grew, the possibilities to recreate a sound space increased.

2.1.2 A new approach to sound design: Procedural Audio

Procedural audio is a concept that has been growing stronger in the past years in the context of computer generated sound and music. It has been defined by Andy Farnell as: “Sound as a process rather than sound as a data“ [2] and introduces a different approach to the sound design process that doesn’t grow from pre-recorded sound and music but from the concept of sound as an interactive, non-linear, adaptive process [5]. He also explains the sound generation methods from the stochastic, generative, algorithmic and AI sound perspectives. Additionally, Cécile Picard also defends the importance of physics and sound perception in the sound design process in her PhD Thesis [6] where she addresses the problem of sound rendering in virtual environments from physically based synthesis models, signal-based and empirical approaches .

2.1.3 Evaluation and methods for sound design

Even do different signal processing techniques and approaches had been discussed in the sound design field [7] [2] [8], not many evaluation tools had been developed.

The CLOSED project presented by IRCAM aimed to close the loop of sound evaluation and design [9] by defining a framework of the sound design process that considers its physical, interaction and psychological attributes. It also proposed an evaluation tool that measures the sound’s function, aesthetics, and emotion components.

On the other hand, the research carried out by Liljedahl [1], proposed a system that allowed to perform a simulation to analyze how a sound would behave in a given auditory context and therefore help in the decision-making process.

2.1.4 Sounds of nature in film

Nature sound had played an important role in different films. In the movie *Castaway*² the director Robert Zemeckis wanted the sound effects to fill the sound space from the moment Tom Hanks boards the airplane that sparks his adventure on the island and until the time he leaves it. Since music wasn't going to be present, the sound designer Randy Thom had to use elements as waves, winds, breaths, grunts and foley [10]. For the waves sound, every single wave was cut individually and mix along with many other water sounds that were recorded for this task. The wind was also a very important element in the movie especially because at a particular moment it needed to give to the Tom Hanks character the clue that the wind changed its direction and blew stronger away from the island at a specific time of the year, in order to do this Randy Thom and his team recorded a variety of wind sounds from different locations [11] that at the end gave them the sound palette to accomplish what they wanted. This along with the changes in dynamics between sounds produced the final result of the sound design process for the movie.

Another vision on sounds of nature for film is given by the movie *Finding Nemo*³ in which the underwater sound was a huge part of the sound design. The sound designer Gary Rydstrom along with his team recorded a variety of audio samples in small aquariums [12] and for some cases they used a hydrophone⁴. They also recorded the sound of the waves splashing onto the rocks to recreate the sound of the interaction between the water and a whale. For some cases they used the sound design workstation Kyma⁵ to perform morphing techniques and to produce underwater growling sounds, using as one input the ocean sound as a the second input Rydstrom's voice.

2.1.5 The concept of the speaking sea in media

By the time this thesis was presented we hadn't found many speaking sea examples in media. However we did find two commercials presented by the company Royal Caribbean in which the speaking sea is a male voice for the Spanish version⁶ and a female voice for the English version⁷. In these videos, the concept of the sea is not implicit as the true character of the voice is slowly revealed through the stories and then finally disclosed when the voice presents itself as the sea.

2.2 Digital Audio Effects

2.2.1 Digital Audio effects

Digital Audio Effects are the signal processing techniques used to modify a given sound in order to produce a perceptual difference. These techniques might be applied in the time domain, frequency domain or in both domains.

Research in this domain has led to the creation of the European research project named EUCOST-G6 "Digital Audio Effects" [7]. Since 1997, year in which the project started, several conferences had taken place in different cities around the world. The initial project ended in 2001, however the DAFX conferences had been established as the

²<http://www.imdb.com/title/tt0162222/>

³<http://www.pixar.com/featurefilms/nemo/>

⁴<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hydrophone>

⁵<http://www.symbolicsound.com/cgi-bin/bin/view/Company/WebHome>

⁶https://www.youtube.com/watch?feature=player_embedded&v=HboQJ_Jyb3c

⁷https://www.youtube.com/watch?feature=player_embedded&v=H2KTmLjTz7E

place for researchers to present their work in the field. This work has led to the book DAFX Digital Audio Effects [13], in which a broad collection of signal processing techniques in the context of audio effects is presented.

2.2.2 Classification of Digital Audio effects

Classification of DAFX has been done based on the different approaches applied to modify the input signal. Primary, taking into account the technical language of the creator (DSP engineer) rather than the perceptual changes perceived by the user (performer, sound engineer, etc).

In the literature the following classifications had been defined: signal processing classification [13] [14] [15] [16], perceptual classification [17], sound and music classification and control type classification [18]. In 2006, an interdisciplinary approach to audio effect classification [19] proposed a transverse classification that takes into account the signal processing techniques and perceptual result of the audio effects in order to facilitate communication between composers, sound designers, DSP engineers, performers, musicologists and other professionals involved in the digital audio effects field.

Classification based on perceptual attributes:

This classification scheme is focused on the perceptual attributes produced by the audio effects.

Figure 1. Audio Effects classification based on the perceptual features. [19]

Classification based on underlying techniques:

This classification is based on the techniques used to implement different the audio effects.

Figure 2. Audio Effects classification based on the underlying techniques used to implement hem. DF stands for frequency Domain and TD stands for time domain. [19]

Classification based on an Interdisciplinary approach:

The audio effects classification proposed in [19] organizes the different attributes of the effect from low level features to high level features. First presents the digital implementation technique followed by the processing domain and the applied processing. Second, discusses the control type and finally introduce the perceptual attributes and the semantic descriptors (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Interdisciplinary diagram for the wah-wah effect. [19]

2.3 Speech Processing

Speech processing is a growing field of research. It involves categories such as speech recognition, speaker identification, speech coding, speech synthesis and voice analysis among others. In 2000 Ben Gold and Nelson Morgan introduced their book: "Speech and Audio signal processing" [20]. They addressed topics such as acoustics, auditory perception, automatic speech recognition and synthesis and coding as a means for setting the theoretical bases in the speech processing field and contribute with a starting point for future developments and improvements in the subject.

In 2005 John Coleman presented the book: "Introducing speech and language processing" [21] as a starting point for students who wanted to get involved in the speech processing area and had a background in different disciplines such as arts, humanities, linguistics, psychology, speech science and engineering. In this book he discusses topics including digital signal processing, speech analysis and synthesis, acoustics and automatic speech recognition, additionally, he includes examples written in C as a supporting tool for his teaching method.

2.3.1 Speech Production

Speech is a main aspect in human communication. Speech production starts from the moment in which the brain sends the information of what we want to say and involves four stages: Initiation, phonation, oro-nasal process and articulation [22].

The initiation process is present when air is expelled from the lungs, then the phonation process starts as the air goes through the larynx and interacts with the vocal folds and the glottis. If the glottis has a narrow opening once the air passes through, a voice sound is produced as a result of the friction created against the vocal folds that makes them vibrate, if the glottis is completely open then a voiceless sound is produced, this results in a noisy sound. Once the air has passed it will go through the nasal and oral cavities. And finally the articulation process will occur in the mouth according to the positions of different articulators such as teeth, tongue and upper and lower lip.

2.3.2 Source Filter Processing and Vocoder

In speech production, the source filter model implies the combination of two aspects, the first one are the vocal folds acting as the excitation signal, and the second one are the mouth and nose cavities acting as the resonator. We can observe the behavior of the source filter system when looking at its spectral envelope. The spectral envelope is a smoothed version of the spectrum that discards the spectral line structure but at the same time preserves the general form [13].

In order to apply a source filter transformation we need to perform two steps: First, we need to estimate the spectral envelope, and second we need to do a source-filter separation in order to make a transformation in one of them, once that process has been done, we do a sound filter combination.

For doing this, three techniques can be used:

- Channel Vocoder: This technique uses frequency bands and calculates the RMS values for each band to estimate the spectral envelope.
- Linear Prediction: This technique estimates an all-pole filter that represents the spectral envelope of a sound.
- Cepstrum: The cepstrum technique performs a smoothing of the logarithm of the FFT spectrum as a means to separate its spectral envelope and its source signal.

2.4 Activity and Valence in music and speech

Activity and valence are well known concepts in music performance since they shape a two dimensional space used to describe emotional expression [23]. Activity Relates to high and low energy and valence relates to positive and negative emotions. This leads to the characterization of four emotional states:

High activity, Positive Valence: Happiness

High activity, Negative Valence: Angry

Low activity, Positive Valence: Tenderness

Low activity, Negative Valence: Sadness

Figure No. 4 Activity-Valence two-dimensional space [24]

This two-dimensional space has also been defined as a way to structure emotions in speech. In 2009 Koolagudi et al [25], presented their work on emotion detection from speech data using spectral features. They used a database containing 8 emotions along a two dimensional emotion plane. The arousal axis corresponds to “loudness in expression” [25] and the valence axis stands for positivism or negativity of the emotion. For some emotions such as Angry and Happy there is not a significant difference along the Arousal axis, however this difference increases regarding the valence axis.

Figure 5. Two dimensional emotion plane. (A = Anger, C = Compassion/Sad, D = Disgust, F = Fear, H = Happy, N = Neutral, S = Sarcastic, Su= Surprise)

MFCC were used as a means to classify emotions along the valence axis, since this positivism or negativity of emotions in speech can be observed analyzing the articulators to estimate the vocal effort. Additionally they apply a Gaussian Mixture Model to shape the distribution of each of the 8 emotions. A maximum of 78% - 80% emotion recognition was obtained for single male and female speakers respectively.

3. METHODOLOGY

The sound of nature chosen to implement the cross synthesis model was the sound of the sea. First, we looked for elements of the sea that served as the base to describe its behavior and to establish a concept.

3.1 Sea concept

Earth is composed in a 70 % by water, oceans and seas occupy 361 000 000 km² of the earth's surface⁸. Seas can be seen as smaller water masses that at some point meet the oceans or as the general group of seas and oceans.

The sound produced by the sea waves carries a message that explains the state of the sea at a particular time and place. Waves produced by the sea are not constant in terms of their velocity, their strength, the direction, and the their continuity. This changes depend on the weather conditions, the psychical conditions of the place where the sea has been formed, if a particular sea flows into a bigger one, etc.

As one example, the friction produced against the wind may cause bigger and more continuous waves to create a “stronger sea” or smaller and occasional waves to transmit a “calmer” sea, this behavior can be interpreted as an emotional state of the sea .

The emotional state in speech, is part of the prosody of an utterance, it is given by the rhythm, stress and intonation of speech. The syllable length, the pitch and the loudness are factors that help printing and emotion in speech. If we perform an analogy of prosody in speech but from the waves behavior point of view, then the waves length, loudness and continuity could be the starting point for defining the mechanism of how the sea would speak.

If we consider that syllables are clustered phonemes that allow a natural rhythm in speak⁹, it would make sense to think that the rhythm of the sea could be given by the waves and therefore, we could pair each syllable to a wave as part of the prosody of the speaking sea.

The Table No 1 shows the fragmentation of the sentence: Once upon a time.

Word	Syllable 1	Syllable 2
Once	Once	
Upon	U	pon
A	A	
Time	Time	

Table No 1 . Example of the sentence “Once upon a time” and its syllable fragmentation

⁸<http://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Oc%C3%A9ano>

⁹Applied Speech and Audio Processing, pag 40.

Once we have analyzed the syllables fragmentation of the sentence, we can observe more elements that are present in speech prosody and that we want to explore in the speaking sea concept.

It is important to notice that in this thesis we focused on the english language. For other languages elements as the number of phonemes and the information than the pitch and the formants convey could be very different. In english, intelligibility increases when the second and third formant (F2 and F3) are present. The tone itself doesn't contribute much to the intelligibility of the message however in tonal languages as mandarin the meaning of the message depends on the tone.

Volume in english normal speech, depends on the phoneme class. The averaged amplitude of a vowel is approximately 12 dB louder than the averaged amplitude of a consonant [26]. As in speech, the volume perceived when the waves reach the shore is not constant, it depends on different elements, such as the weather conditions. Even in a sea of stable behavior we'll notice that waves arrive with different volumes that depend on the characteristics of the previous wave. And they also arrive at different times, some waves are closer than others, just as the syllabic rate is. Being able to pair each wave to a syllable allow us to play with changes in the volume, and the syllabic rate and observe how they affect the quality and intelligibility of the message.

In speech, not always meaningful speech information is produced, pauses are taken and fillers such as such as “uh” and “mmm” are present, also breathing is constant, this means that there's always something sounding, just as in the sea.

In the case of the sea we can explore ambience sounds, as part of this continuity behavior and generate utterances in which some waves contain speech information and some others don't.

3.2 Gathering the waves and voice recordings database

3.2.1 Voice Recordings

Considering that one of the main applications of this thesis would be its use in the sound design process for film, media, etc., we chose a number of famous film quotes and common short story quotes to be recorded. From the sentences presented in table No2 we used four to perform the evaluation test (see chapter 4).

Film Quote – Story Line	Movie/Year
Bond, James Bond	Dr No. (1962)
Houston we have a problem	Apollo 13 (1995)
Frankly my dear I don't give a damn	Gone with the wind (1939)
I'll be back	The Terminator (1984)
Once upon a time	
And they lived happily ever after	
Once upon a time, there was a little girl named Goldilocks	Goldilocks

Table No 2. Film Quotes

We wanted to print the idea of the sea prosody from the voice recording, so different intonations and syllabic rates were tried. Regarding pitch, we recorded the voice as a whisper because this way we get closer to the sound produced by the sea, which can be modeled as filtered white noise. In other words, the recorded whisper utterance is a noisy signal, with similar characteristics to the sound of the sea. The comparison of the spectral envelopes of a sea recording, a whispered utterance of the word “once” and a non-whispered utterance of the same word can be observed in figure No 7. All recordings were made at a sample rate of 44100 samples/sec and WAV format.

Figure No 6. Whispered utterance of the syllable “Once”

Figure No 7. Comparison of spectral envelopes: sea, whispered “once”, non-whispered once.

The voice recording equipment

We used two different microphones, a dynamic and a condenser to test the recording quality and observe if intelligibility increased with one or another.

The dynamic microphone was a Shure C 606 and the condenser was a M-Audio Nova.

The following table, compares the technical specifications of the two microphones.

Shure C 606 ¹⁰ 	
Dynamic	Condenser
Polar pattern: Cardioid	Polar pattern: Cardioid
Frequency response: 50 Hz to 15000 Hz	Frequency response: 20 Hz to 18000 Hz
Sensitivity: -52 dBV/Pa (1000 Hz)	Sensitivity: 16 mV/Pa (-36dBV)
Impedance: 600 ohms	Impedance: 200 ohms

Table No 3. Microphones specs comparison

Once we tried different recordings with both microphones we decided to work with the condenser, as this type of technology works with phantom power (48 V) and it requires less gain at the preamp of the sound card to have the same recording input level as a dynamic mic. What we get, if the recording chain has been set up properly and the electric and acoustic conditions of the room are good, is a less noisy recording.

Another good characteristic of the condenser was to count on a wider frequency range because, it gave us more detail and allowed us to experiment with different frequency ranges for the cross-synthesis process.

Figure No 8. Recording and editing chain

We used a pop filter and a shock mount to avoid "puff" and vibration noises.

¹⁰<http://www.musiciansfriend.com/pro-audio/shure-c606-dynamic-microphone>

¹¹http://www.m-audio.com/products/en_us/Nova.html

Figure No 9. Voice recordings setup

3.2.2 Sea Recordings

The sea recordings were made using the Edirol Portable Recorder R1. We gathered most of the recordings from Barcelona's beach and its breakwaters and a few from Alicante's beach. Some of the recordings were made close to the source in order to capture single waves and others were meant to capture more ambience.

We wanted to build a diverse database of sea sounds in order to use some excerpts for voice synthesis and some others for ambience, however the ambience of the samples included in the test, was built from the single waves recordings, not the ambience recordings. We generated the ambience from single waves because this allowed us to obtain a more coherent sound since the utterance is built upon a similar base. Using single waves also opens a possibility for future work of using the wave's descriptors and wave's times as a tool to build a desired sea ambience (brighter, faster, stronger, calmer, etc). Also, if waves from different seas are gathered then it would be possible to have options such as the “Mediterranean” and “Atlantic” Version of an utterance. However, using pre-recorded ambiences containing sounds like the waves crushing against cliffs breakwaters or sea water caves, or even general sea ambience recordings, etc., should be explored as part of the future work.

All recordings were made stereo, WAV format and at a sample rate of 44100 samples/sec.

Figure No 10. Portable Recorder R1

Edirol R1 ¹²
Number of tracks: 2 (stereo)
Recording Sampling Rate: 44.1 kHz
Main Audio input: Internal Stereo Microphone (omni-directional back electret type microphones).

Table No 4. Edirol R1 technical specifications.

¹²<http://www.roland.com/products/en/R-1/>

When recording outdoors, there are always different sounds that might be unwanted and considered noise depending on the purpose of the recording. For this project, noises like the wind or people talking at the beach needed to be treated.

Gathering the single waves is not an easy task, it depends on the recording equipment and the weather conditions. It is possible to obtain single waves however, by single wave we don't mean completely isolated but definitely strong and clear enough to be by far the most important element in the recording. The sea is always sounding and there are elements that are going to be present daily, for example: animals, people, airplanes, boats, etc., however many of these unwanted components might be mitigated by observing how the sea is behaving the day of the recording, and chose the best possible points of the shore to place the recording devices.

In our case, to stop as much as possible the wind noise, we made a windshield out of foam and when the day was very windy we also added a thick sock. The fact that the Edirol R1's microphones were omnidirectional made harder to avoid people's noises, so we focused on recording at a certain places and times in which the beach was less busy. However, many of these people's noises could be avoided using microphones with a cardioid polar pattern and this will open the possibility to try different stereo recording techniques for close miking (single waves) and distant miking (ambience).

Once we had the recordings, we edited the audios to start building a database of single waves.

3.3 Waves and syllables characterization

3.3.1 Waves characterization

The waves database was gathered during different days and seasons of the year, therefore the volume, brightness, duration and general behavior of each wave was different.

We wanted to be able to characterize these differences using descriptors to later on built a system in which the proper wave was selected according to the characteristics of each syllable, based mainly on its phonemes information. However we didn't get to develop this part of the project, what we did was to extract a number of timbre descriptors to get a visual feedback of a waves behavior. We used the the MIRToolbox¹³ to extract the following descriptors:

- Global Energy
- Centroid
- Brightness

These descriptors were not calculated over the whole wave. We defined five points that allowed us to establish four segments that are clearly present in regular sea waves and that could help us describe them and achieve a more credible utterance.

The four segments that we considered important to describe the wave were:

¹³<https://www.jyu.fi/hum/laitokset/musiikki/en/research/coe/materials/mirtoolbox>

- Segment 1: Start of the audio (Point 1)¹⁴ to start of the wave (Point 2)
- Segment 2: Start of the wave (Point 2) to brake Point (Point 3)
- Segment 3: Brake Point (Point 3) to post brake point (Point 4)
- Segment 4: Post brake point (Point 4) to end of the wave (Point 5)

Each of the descriptors is calculated over each of the four segments. The result is a table as the one presented in table No.

Figure No 11. Image of a sea wave

Figure No 12. Waveform of a sea wave recording

¹⁴The first point always has zero value.

Wave Number	Brightness			
	Segment 1	Segment 2	Segment 3	Segment 4
Wave 1	0.4722	0.5429	0.5483	0.5556
Wave 2	0.5116	0.5223	0.5607	0.4627
Wave 3	0.5173	0.4746	0.6005	0.7074
Wave 4	0.5443	0.4766	0.6004	0.6885
Wave 5	0.2727	0.4267	0.4669	0.3484
Wave 6	0.3211	0.4683	0.4968	0.4274
Wave 7	0.5852	0.5070	0.5501	0.5419
Wave 8	0.4350	0.3857	0.4595	0.5258
Wave 9	0.6267	0.5286	0.4919	0.5983
Wave 10	0.5130	0.4692	0.6724	0.6212
Wave 11	0.5191	0.5468	0.5099	0.5339
Wave 12	0.5211	0.3983	0.5093	0.5701
Wave 13	0.4194	0.5349	0.5042	0.5880
Wave 14	0.5137	0.4713	0.5531	0.5922

Table No 5. Values of brightness for a set of waves calculated over the four segments.

These points were obtained manually by listening and looking to the single wave recording using an audio editor. For each wave audio file a .txt file containing the values of the points was created.

3.3.2 Syllables characterization

We used a phonetic transcription to decompose each sentence in words, syllables and phonemes, this allowed us to know the phoneme classes and accentuations present in the each line.

The phonetic transcription used is the Unisyn Lexicon developed by Susan Fitt from the Centre for Speech Technology Research at the University of Edinburgh¹⁵.

The input to the system is a .txt file containing a text. For example the sentence: "Houston we have a problem". The output of the system is the phonetic transcription presented as follows:

```

/ Houston we have a problem
/ [Sil] [" h j u . s t @ n] [w i] [" h { v] [@] [" p r A . b 5 @ m] [Sil]
Sil h j u s t @ n w i h { v @ p r A b 5 @ m Sil

```

The first line contains the initial text, the second one presents the words and silences of the sentence separated by square brackets. Each word includes the syllables separation represented by a point (.). The third line includes all the phonemes and silences without separations.

Once we have the phonetic transcription we use a MATLAB script to get and separate each word of the second line of the transcription and then look for syllables if there are any. We establish two lists, one containing the words and one containing the syllables. Using this method we know how many syllables there are in a word and how many there are in the total sentence, therefore we know how many waves we'll need to generate the final utterance and we'll see how a word is composed.

¹⁵<http://www.cstr.ed.ac.uk/projects/unisyn/>

Word	Syllables	Phonemes
Houston	" h j u /s t @ n]	h j u s t @ n
We	w i	w i
Have	" h { v	h { v
A	@	@
Problem	p r A . b 5 @ m	p r A b 5 @ m

Table No 6. Structure of the sentence “Houston, we have a problem”

The table No 5 shows the words structure and phonetic transcription of the the sentence: “Houston we have a problem” from the movie Apollo 13 (1995).

Accentuations

Accentuated syllables are marked by this symbol ‘” ’ in the phonetic transcription, we use the accentuation information to create a gain vector in which accentuated syllables had more gain than the unaccented ones.

Times vector depending on words composition

We used the syllable composition of a word to create a times vector. This way, if a word had two or more syllables, these would be closer in time than monosyllables words. This allowed us to play with the syllable rate and to create a faster or slower speaking sea.

3.4 Source-filter processing

The Source Filter model considers the excitation produced in the vocal folds as the source signal and the vocal and nasal cavities as the filter or resonator system.

There are different methods to extract these two components of a voice signal, we chose the cepstrum technique.

In order to perform voice synthesis from sounds of nature and voice recordings, we followed these steps to carry out the sound-filter transformation:

- Estimate the spectral envelope
- Perform the source-filter separation and after the transformation of one or the other perform a sound-filter combination.

3.4.1 Cepstrum

The cepstrum permits the estimation of a spectral envelope, it is the inverse Fourier transform of the logarithm of the spectrum of a signal. Using this technique it is possible to separate the source signal and the spectral envelope of the signal. This separation is produced by the following mathematical property:

$$\log a \cdot b = \log(a) + \log(b)$$

What we accomplish is a separation of the slow varying part of the signal (the filter) and the fast varying part of the signal (the source). In order to do this, a cut-off frequency needs to be defined, if this value is too low the resulting envelope will be too smooth and if it is too high it will follow the spectrum too much including the anti-resonances between the spectral peaks¹⁶. This source-filter separation is an approximation, this means that it is not perfect, in fact it is dependent of values like the cut-off frequency.

3.4.2 Cross Synthesis

Figure No 13. Basic principle of homomorphic (based on cepstrum analysis) cross-synthesis¹⁷

The cross-synthesis effect combines two sounds by applying the spectral shape of the second sound to the first sound while preserving the pitch of the first sound.

Cross-synthesis from sounds of nature and voice recordings

The main idea of the cross-synthesis effect, is to take two inputs and generate a third output that combines the characteristic of the two previous sounds.

To perform voice synthesis from sounds of nature and voice recordings we estimate the spectral envelope of both sounds using the cepstrum method.

The sound 1 is a sea recording, more exactly, a single wave. By inverse filtering this sound we obtain the source. The second sound is a voice recording containing one syllable, using the cepstrum method we get the formants (filter).

We filter the first sound by the second sound, preserving the pitch of the first sound and the formants of the second sound.

¹⁶U. Zölzer, DAFX: Digital Audio Effects. Pag 294.

¹⁷U. Zölzer, DAFX: Digital Audio Effects. Pag 304.

Figure No 14. Spectral Envelope Source and Filter

Spectral envelope normalization

In order to perform the cross-synthesis we do a normalization since the amplitude of the source (40 dB) and the filter (-60 dB) are very different.

In the frequency domain, we average the spectral envelopes of both sounds in order to estimate the amplitude of the filter that we'll apply to the source, however if we do this linearly we'll find that for a given frequency bandwidth related to the voice range, the amplitude of the sea can decay quickly and drag down the amplitude of the formants and lead to a loss of intelligibility.

In order to improve this, we perform a polynomial regression, we estimate the coefficients of the polynomial and obtain the amplitude of the filter but taking into account the overall behavior of the spectral envelope of the source. We do this in dB for the values of the polynomial no to go below zero. This filter is applied in a given frequency range (e.g. 400 Hz to 5000 Hz) and it has a fade in and fade out at the beginning and end of the defined interval.

Figure No 15. Spectral Envelope Estimation – Polynomial Regression

Source-filter Combination

Once we've performed the normalization and estimated the spectral envelope of both sounds we shape spectrally the first sound (source) by the second sound (filter), this process is done in dB. We take the filter's spectral envelope and apply it to the source on a given frequency range related to the voice (e.g. 300 Hz and 4000 Hz), outside this range the filter has a zero dB value, which means that there are no modifications in the amplitude.

Figure No 16. Cross-synthesis (600 Hz - 4000 Hz)

Time Scaling

The cross-synthesis transformation was not only limited to a frequency range but also to a time range. We used the waves points mentioned in section 3.3, to perform the cross-synthesis only between given points.

After trying different time intervals for the processing, we chose the starting point (p1) of the wave until the post breaking point (p3) to create the evaluation test utterances. This way, we could explore the sound that waves produce once they are approximating to the shore, when they brake and when they arrive to the beach.

Then, we time scaled the voice recordings to the duration of the wave in between the predefined processing time points (g.e. From p1 to p3).

Initially we were performing an even time scaling, so we time scaled the whole syllable in the same proportion. However stretching some consonants didn't sound natural, so we decided to lengthen in a bigger proportion the vowels. In order to do this, manually we obtained the duration and location of the vowels part of a syllable and created a .txt file containing four points:

- Syllable start
- Vowel start
- Vowel end
- Syllable end

Once we have these points we can determine how long in samples are the syllable and the wave section to morph (between point 1 and point 3) and stretch the syllable to the waves duration.

3.5 Mix

Once we've generated the speaking waves, we generate an ambience background out of single waves recordings and built the complete utterance.

Gain

The gain of the each syllable is given but the accentuation vector mentioned in section 3.3, The gain of the ambience can be established manually.

Panning

The speaking waves are panned center. For the ambience we generate two layers, one panned to the left and the other panned to the right [range: 0 (left) to 1 (right)]. The panning value can be adjusted for each utterance. .

Figure No 17. Mix chain

3.6 Cross-synthesis Algorithm (Overall Processing)

The cross-synthesis overall processing algorithm is composed by different functions that contribute to the generation of the final utterance.

Choosing the transcription file

The first step is to choose a transcription file. Each transcription file obtained using the Unisyn Lexicon, is stored in a .txt file with the name of the sentence or famous quote and an ID number, for example, the sentence “Houston we have a problem” corresponds to the “sentence2”. Then, another function extracts the number of words and syllables, including the accentuation information from the transcription.

Finding the corresponding voice recordings from the database

From the name of the transcription file “Houston_we_have_a_problem_sentence2” it is possible to find another .txt file that contains the names of the syllables that form the original quote or sentence, so the system finds the corresponding audio in the syllables database.

Choosing the waves

As for choosing the waves, once we know how many syllables we need to process, it is possible to randomly pick that same number of waves from the waves database, to generate the cross-synthesis. From this information we also generate the value of the total duration of the ambience vector since its length depends on the number of syllables. The ambience is build from the waves database in order to fill the total duration previously defined. We also determine a vector that indicates in which part of the ambience vector (seconds) will the cross-synthesis audios be added. If a word has two or more syllables, then this audios are closer in time in comparison to monosyllables words that need to be more separated.

Applying panning and gain values

We are able to chose the panning and gain values for the ambience. This version of the algorithm generates two ambience layers, if we defined the panning value as 0.1 where 0 is completely to he left and 1 completely to the right, the the algorithm will generate one ambience layer to the left (0.1) and another layer to the right at panning value (0.9), each layer is made from different waves. The gain value can be set from 0 to 1.

The gain values of each syllable are given by the accentuation information obtained from the phonetic transcription.

The output is an utterance that holds all the processed syllables corresponding to the phonetic transcription and the ambience layers.

Figure No 18. Cross-synthesis chart

4. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

We conducted a listening test, four generated utterances were chosen and evaluated using the MOS (Mean Opinion Score) scale. The following aspects were asked.

Aspect A: The intelligibility of the message

Aspect B: The sound Quality

Aspect C: Does the synthesized sound preserves the characteristics of the sound of the sea?

Score	Description
5	Excellent
4	Good
3	Fair
2	Poor
1	Bad

Table No. 7 Mean Opinion Score (MOS) Scale

The test was divided in two parts. During the first part, people listened to an utterance and evaluated aspect A, aspect B and aspect C. In the second part, the text sentence was presented to them and they evaluated once again aspect A, aspect B and aspect C. They also evaluated if intelligibility increased after they were shown the original text. The idea of evaluating before and after presenting the sentence was also to introduce the sea model to the listeners, since it is not easy to have a reference of how it might sound and many elements can be expected at the same time.

A total number of 13 people took the listening test.

Test conditions:

People with different backgrounds took the test, there were no special prerequisites other than being familiar with the english language.

It was highly recommended to use headphones and a specialized sound card during the test.

Test condition	Percentage Values
People who took the test using headphones.	61,53 %
People who took the test using a specialized sound system (stereo, 2,1, 5.1).	23,07 %
People who took the test using the computer's regular speakers.	15,38 %
People who took the test using a specialized sound card.	7,69 %
People who took the test using the computer's regular sound card.	92,30 %

Table No. 8 Test technical conditions

Evaluated Sentences:

- Once upon a time
- Houston we have a problem
- And they lived happily ever after
- Once upon a time there was a girl named Goldilocks.

Sound quality of the utterance and Intelligibility of the message:

Sentence	First Part	Aspect A	Aspect B	Second Part	Aspect A	Aspect B
Once upon a time		3,07	1,69		2,69	2,15
Houston we have a problem	2,46	1,92	2,69	1,76		
And they lived happily ever after	2,69	2	2,46	1,61		
Once upon a time there was a girl named Goldilocks	2,84	2,3	3	1,53		

Table No. 9 MOS – sound quality of the utterance and intelligibility of the message

- Percentage of people who considered that intelligibility increased once the line was presented to them: 75 %
- The results show that intelligibility decreases as the number of syllables in the sentence increases. This could be the result of the low intelligibility of plosives phonemes that increase the difficulty level to understand the message.
- Most of the test participants took the test using the computer's regular sound card and around 38% didn't used headphones to listen to the audio samples. This might have taken away quality and therefore intelligibility, however, it was mentioned for some participants that understanding the syllables was difficult because the consonants weren't clear enough, meanwhile vowels were clearer.

Sea concept (Aspect C):

The following graph presents the answers to the question: Does the synthesized sound preserves the characteristics of the sea?

*Values in percentage (%).

Graph No 1. Answers to the test question:

The defined sea concept was mostly considered to preserve the characteristics of the sea and to be aesthetically good.

The sea concept:

We also asked two members of the MTG (Music Technology Group) at University Pompeu Fabra to answer to the question “If it could, how do you think that the sea would speak?”.

Carlos Vaquero SMC Master, UPF:

““ Maybe you could try to use a constant background and shorter waves combined with "hard" waves to accentuate some consonants.

I also think about the possibility of using the see as if you would be in a cave so that you could use some of the properties of the reverberation of the cave.””

Panos Papiotis PhD Student, Music Technology Group, UPF:

“I think it would speak slowly, without intonation or rhythm. But since the sea doesn't speak, I guess that there is no single correct way to make the sea 'speak' - it depends on what is the purpose behind giving the sea a voice.”

5. CONCLUSIONS

- The concept we addressed for the speaking sea was mainly considered as a credible representation of the sea's characteristics.
- There are different points of view on how the sea could speak as presented on sections 2.1.5 and 4. These ideas could differ or complement the concept exposed trough this document, in the end, many ideas are valid depending on what is the purpose of the speaking sea, for example, if it is to convey a complete message or to give the sensation that the sea is talking.

- The recording process is fundamental to avoid unwanted noises from the beginning. It could also provide different sound colors and quality improvements to the final result.
- The intelligibility of a phoneme increases or decreases depending on the chosen filter's frequency range. Vowels tend to have lower formants and therefore the filter can perform well when having a middle cut-off frequency. In the case of voiced and unvoiced plosives the cut-off frequency needs to be higher. This could be improved by implementing an active frequency band that varies depending on the phoneme of each frame, the starting point would be the phonetic transcription.
- Plosive phonemes are more difficult to synthesize
- The intelligibility of the message is highly dependent on the consonants.
- Vowels are easier to understand because of its bigger energy content.
- The cross-synthesis technique provides a wide range of possibilities to develop the speaking sea model, however it is still needed to work on the synthesis of consonants, especially the plosives, as a mean to improve the overall intelligibility.

6. FUTURE WORK

Improving the speaking sea model:

- Generate a waves “chooser” based on descriptors to pick the proper wave to each syllable .
- Explore machine learning techniques to establish the cross-synthesis frequency range that best suites the needs of each syllable depending on its phonetic composition.
- Build a bigger waves database, including recordings from different seas and gathered with several recording techniques and microphones.
- Explore different voice synthesis techniques that could improve the performance of the speaking sea model recording plosive phonemes.

Building a set of speaking nature models:

- Explore and define the speaking concept for other sounds of nature or phenomena, for example: volcano, thunder, rain.
- Explore more voice synthesis techniques to generate credible utterances from sounds of nature and voices.

Go further in testing the speaking nature models

- Perform the sound design of a short clip or animation including the sounds of nature utterances.
- Include stereo, 5.1 and audio 3D mixes to evaluate the quality and intelligibility of the utterances in different audio systems and acoustics scenarios.
- Evaluate if the sounds of nature are perceived as credible when included in a sound scenario containing more sound elements.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] M. Liljedahl, J.Fagerlönn, “Methods for sound design: a review and implications for research and practice”. Proceedings of the 5th Audio Mostly Conference: A Conference on Interaction with Sound, NY, USA 2010.
- [2] A. Farnell, Designing Sound. 2010.
- [3] <http://www.associationofsounddesigners.com/whatis>, Accessed on March 2012.
- [4] <http://lavender.fortunecity.com/hawkslane/575/sound-in-films.htm>, Accessed on March 2012.
- [5] A. Farnell, “An introduction to procedural audio and its application in computer games”. September 2007.
- [6] C. Picard, “Expressive Sound Synthesis for Animation”. PhD Thesis, University of Nice - Sophia Antipolis. (2009).
- [7]. <http://www.dafx.de/>
- [8] P. R. Cook, Real Sound synthesis for interactive applications, 2002.
- [9] <http://closed.ircam.fr>, Accessed on March 2012.
- [10]http://web.archive.org/web/20050518085639/http://www.editorsguild.com/newsletter/MayJun01/sound_cast_away.html, accessed on March 2012.
- [11] http://mixonline.com/mag/audio_harnessing_elements_cast/
- [12]<http://web.archive.org/web/20040522035443/http://audiomedia.com/redesign-2003/regionalissues/issue-european/2003/2003-06/html/uk-0603-fc/0603-fc.htm>, Accessed on March 2012.
- [13] U. Zölzer, DAFX: Digital Audio Effects. J. Wiley & Sons,2002.
- [14] S. Orfanidis, “Introduction to Signal Processing”. Prentice Hall Int. Editions, 1996.
- [15] C. Roads, The Computer Music Tutorial. Cambridge, Massachusetts: MIT Press, 1996.
- [16] F. Richard Moore, Elements of Computer Music. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice Hall,1990.
- [17] X. Amatriain, J. Bonada, A. Loscos, J. L. Arcos, and V. Verfaillie, “Content-based transformations,” J. New Music Research, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 95–114, 2003.
- [18]. V. Verfaillie, Marcelo M. Wanderley and P. Depalle. “Mapping strategies for gestural control of adaptive digital audio effects”. J. New Music Research, vol 35, no. 1, pp. 71-93, 2006.
- [19] V. Verfaillie, C. Guastavino and C. Traube. “An interdisciplinary approach to audio effect classification”. 9th Int. Conf. Digital Audio Effects (DAFx-06), Montreal, Canada, pp 107-13, 2006.
- [20] B. Gold and N. Morgan, Speech and Audio Signal Processing, 2000.
- [21] J. Coleman. Speech and Language Processing, Cambridge University Press, 2005.
- [22] http://www.ugr.es/~ftsaez/fonetica/production_speech.pdf
- [23]. Friberg, A. (2006). pDM: an expressive sequencer with real-time control of the KTH music performance rules. Computer Music Journal, 30(1), 37-48.
- [24] <http://www-scf.usc.edu/~ise575/b/projects/mardirossian/3.html>. Accessed on March 2012.
- [25] S.G. Koolagudi and K.S. Rao, “Exploring Speech Features for Classifying Emotions along Valence Dimension”. In Proceedings of PReMI. 2009, 537-542.
- [26] Ian McLoughlin, Applied speech and audio processing, Cambridge University Press 2009.

Appendix A

Cross-synthesis Code

```
% UX_cross_synthesis_cepstrum_white.m [DAFXbook, 2nd ed.,
chapter 8]
% ==== This function performs a cross-synthesis with
cepstrum and whitening
%
%-----
-----
% This source code is provided without any warranties as
published in
% DAFX book 2nd edition, copyright Wiley & Sons 2011,
available at
% http://www.dafx.de. It may be used for educational
purposes and not
% for commercial applications without further permission.
%-----
-----

function [DAFx_out_norm, SR] = crosssynth (file, quote)

%Source/Excitation
[DAFx_sou, SR]= wavread (file); %Source/Excitation
----- %First Input Argument
FileID= strcat(file(1:(end-4)),'.txt'); %Selects txt file
Point = load(FileID); %Wave values

dif =Point(3)-Point(2); %Between Point 2 and Point 3
value= dif/2;

voicesegment = [Point(1) Point(3)-value]*SR; %Wave 2 %Voice

allwavepoints= [Point(1) Point(2)-0.1 Point(3) Point(4)];
allwavepoints_y= [0 0 0 0];

DAFx_env = wavread (quote); % spectral Envelope -----
DAFx_env= DAFx_env(:,1);

doplots_time=0;
t_axis=0:1/SR:(length(DAFx_sou)-1)/SR;
if doplots_time
    figure (5)
    t_axis=0:1/SR:(length(DAFx_sou)-1)/SR;
    plot(t_axis,(DAFx_sou(:,1)), 'c')
%     hold on
%     plot(allwavepoints,(allwavepoints_y),'r*')
%     hold off
    title ('Wave')
    xlabel ('Time (Seconds)')
    ylabel ('Amplitude')
    legend ('source', 'Time Points')
end

end
```

```

doplots=0;
s_win      = 4096*8;    % window size %0.74 sec
n1         = 256*4;    % step increment %23 ms
ovsize     = s_win;%n1*2;    % overlap size
variable_overlap = 0;  % change overlap size along the
syllable??
order_sou  = 30*8;    % cut quefreny for sound 1
order_env  = 30*8;    % cut quefreny for sound 2
r          = 0.99;    % sound output normalizing ratio

%fc=[200,6000]; %Original
fc=[150,18000];

bin=1+round(fc/SR*s_win);
f=[1:s_win]/(s_win-1)*SR;
f=f';

%----- initialisations -----
w1          = hanning(s_win, 'periodic'); % analysis
window
w2          = w1;          % synthesis window
if ovsize<s_win %Centered filter
    w2 = w2*0;
    w2(s_win/2-ovsize/2:s_win/2+ovsize/2) = [0 ;
triang(ovsize-1) ; 0];
end
hs_win      = s_win/2;    % half window size
grain_sou   = zeros(s_win,2); % grain for extracting
source
grain_env    = zeros(s_win,1); % grain for extracting
spec. envelope
pin         = 0;          % start index
%L          = min(length(DAFx_sou),length(DAFx_env));
L = length(DAFx_sou);
pend        = L;          % end index
DAFx_sou    = [zeros(s_win, 2); DAFx_sou; ...
zeros(s_win, 2); zeros(s_win-mod(L,n1),2)] ./
max(abs(DAFx_sou(:)));
DAFx_env    = [zeros(s_win, 1); DAFx_env; ...
zeros(s_win, 1); zeros(s_win-mod(L,n1),1)] /
max(abs(DAFx_env));
DAFx_env(s_win+1:s_win+1+99) =
DAFx_env(s_win+1:s_win+1+99) .* [0:99]'/100;
DAFx_sou(s_win+1:s_win+1+99,:) =
DAFx_sou(s_win+1:s_win+1+99,:) .* [[0:99]' [0:99]']/100;
DAFx_out    = zeros(L+s_win*2,2);
L = length(DAFx_sou);

vowel_info=strcat(quote(1:(end-4)),'.txt');
vowel_info_path=strcat(pwd,'/',vowel_info);
vowel_values=load(vowel_info_path);

% Vowel's values

vp1 = vowel_values(1)*SR; %1; % in samples
vp2 = vowel_values(2)*SR; %1;

```

```

vp3 = vowel_values(3)*SR; %1; % in samples
vp4 = vowel_values(4)*SR;

voice_seg_dur = vp4-vp1; % in samples
morph_seg_dur = voicesegment(2)-voicesegment(1); % number
of samples of the wave section to morph
% voice normalized position

vnp1 = 0;
vnp2 = (vp2-vp1) / voice_seg_dur;
vnp3 = (vp3-vp1) / voice_seg_dur;
vnp4 = 1;

%%
%----- cross synthesis -----
while pin<pend
    grain_sou = DAFx_sou(pin+1:pin+s_win,:).* [ w1 w1 ];
    if pin>=voicesegment(1) && pin<voicesegment(2)

        stretch_vowels = 1;
        if (stretch_vowels)
            % normalized position [0,1] in the wave segment
where we want to hear
            % a voice
            npos = (pin-voicesegment(1)) / morph_seg_dur;
            % mapping to voice normalized position
            ts = morph_seg_dur / voice_seg_dur;
            if ts > 1
                ts = min(2,ts);
                x = [ 0 vnp2/ts 1-(1-vnp3)/ts 1 ];
                y = [ 0 vnp2 vnp3 1 ];
                voice_npos = interp1(x,y,npos,'cubic');
            else
                voice_npos = npos;
            end
            % begin sample of voice frame
            pinvoice = vp1 + round( voice_npos *
voice_seg_dur );
        else
            pinvoice = round((pin-voicesegment(1)) /
(voicesegment(2)-voicesegment(1))*(length(DAFx_env)-s_win-
1));
        end
        grain_env = DAFx_env(pinvoice+1:pinvoice+s_win).* w1;

        %         figure(4)
        %         plot(grain_sou)
        %         hold on
        %         plot(grain_env, 'm')

        %=====
        f_sou      = fft(grain_sou);          % FT of
source  fft sea
        f_env      = fft(grain_env);%/hs_win;    % FT of
filter  fft voice
        %---- computing cepstra ----

```

```

    flog_sou      = log(0.00001+abs(f_sou)); %Logarithm
of the magnitude of fft of the windowed sequence
    cep_sou      = ifft(flog_sou);          % cepstrum
of sound 1 / source sea
    flog_env     = log(0.00001+abs(f_env)); %Logarithm
of the magnitude of fft of the windowed sequence
    cep_env     = ifft(flog_env);          % cepstrum
of sound 2 / env voice.
    %---- liftering cepstra ---- %Fine structure or
formants
    cep_cut_env  = zeros(s_win,1);
    cep_cut_env(1:order_env) = [cep_env(1)/2;
cep_env(2:order_env)];
    flog_cut_env = 2*real(fft(cep_cut_env)); %Cepstrum
env voice
    cep_cut_sou  = zeros(s_win,2);
    cep_cut_sou(1:order_sou,:) = [cep_sou(1,:)/2;
cep_sou(2:order_sou,:)];
    flog_cut_sou = 2*real(fft(cep_cut_sou)); %Cepstrum
source sea
    %---- computing spectral envelope ----

%       figure(1);
%       plot((cep_env)) %Cestrum Voice
%       hold on
%       plot((cep_sou),'m') %Cepstrum Sea
%       hold off
%       pause

    f_env_out = exp(flog_cut_env); %Spectral Envelope Env
    f_sou_out = exp(flog_cut_sou); %Spectral Envelope sou
%
if doplots %spectral Envelope
    figure(2);
    plot(f,20*log10(abs(f_env_out)), 'b')
    hold on
    plot(f,20*log10(abs(f_sou_out)), 'g')
    hold off
    %xlim([0 SR/2])
    title('Spectral Envelope')
    xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
    ylabel('Amplitude (dB)')
    xlim([0 SR/2])
    legend('Filter', 'Source')
    pause
end
%-----Problemas
-----%
% el polyval se va por debajo de cero, hay que hacerlo
en db
    if 1 %1 = polyval ; 0 = lineal
        f_env_out = 20*log10(f_env_out); %dB
        f_sou_out = 20*log10(f_sou_out);
        pp =
polyfit([bin(1):bin(2)],f_env_out(bin(1):bin(2)),3);
        f_env_out_norm = f_env_out;

```

```

        f_env_out_norm(bin(1):bin(2)) =
f_env_out(bin(1):bin(2)) - polyval(pp,bin(1):bin(2));%
mean(f_env_out(bin(1):bin(2)));
        f_sou_out_norm = f_sou_out;
        pp1 =
polyfit([bin(1):bin(2)],f_sou_out(bin(1):bin(2),1),3);
        f_sou_out_norm(bin(1):bin(2),1) =
f_sou_out_norm(bin(1):bin(2),1) -
polyval(pp1,bin(1):bin(2));
%mean(f_sou_out(bin(1):bin(2),1));
        pp2 =
polyfit([bin(1):bin(2)],f_sou_out(bin(1):bin(2),2),3);
        f_sou_out_norm(bin(1):bin(2),2) =
f_sou_out_norm(bin(1):bin(2),2) -
polyval(pp2,bin(1):bin(2));
%mean(f_sou_out(bin(1):bin(2),2));
        if 0
            figure(3);hold off;
            plot(polyval(pp,bin(1):bin(2))) %Estim poly Env
            hold on;plot(polyval(pp1,bin(1):bin(2)),'r')
%Estimation poly sou
            hold on;plot(f_env_out(bin(1):bin(2))) %Spectral
env env
            hold on;plot(f_sou_out(bin(1):bin(2),1),'r')
%Spectral envelope source

            %hold on;plot(polyval(pp2,bin(1):bin(2)),'g')
%stimation poly sou ch2??

            xlabel ('Frequency (Hz)')
            ylabel ('Amplitude dB')
            %pause(0.05)

        end
        H= 10.^(( [f_env_out_norm f_env_out_norm ] -
f_sou_out_norm)/20); % Preserve env dB

        %H=2*H; %Testing Testing Testing

    else
        f_env_out_norm = f_env_out;
        f_env_out_norm(bin(1):bin(2)) =
f_env_out(bin(1):bin(2)) ./ mean(f_env_out(bin(1):bin(2)));
        f_sou_out_norm = f_sou_out;
        f_sou_out_norm(bin(1):bin(2),1) =
f_sou_out_norm(bin(1):bin(2),1) ./
mean(f_sou_out(bin(1):bin(2),1));
        f_sou_out_norm(bin(1):bin(2),2) =
f_sou_out_norm(bin(1):bin(2),2) ./
mean(f_sou_out(bin(1):bin(2),2));
        H= abs([f_env_out_norm f_env_out_norm ] ./
f_sou_out_norm); % Preserve env dB
    end

    H2 = ones(size(H));

```

```

        tw = tukeywin(bin(2)-bin(1)+1,0.5);
        H2(bin(1):bin(2),:) = 1 + (H(bin(1):bin(2),:)-1) .*
[tw tw];
        H2(s_win/2+2:end,:) = conj(H2(s_win/2:-1:2,:));

        % ---- Whitening ----%
        %f_env_out = exp(flog_cut_env - flog_cut_sou); %
whitening with source

        %---- Resynthesis Grain ----%
        %grain      = (real(ifft(f_sou.*f_env_out))).*w2; %
resynthesis grain

        if variable_overlap
            pos = (pin-voicsegment(1)) / (voicsegment(2)-
voicsegment(1)); % relative position in the syllable
[0..1]
            ovsiz = round(s_win / (8-7*pos^0.25));
            ovsiz = ovsiz - mod(ovsiz,2);
            w2 = w2*0;
            w2(s_win/2-ovsiz/2:s_win/2+ovsiz/2) = [0 ;
triang(ovsiz-1) ; 0];
        end
            grain      = (real(ifft(f_sou.*H2))).*[w2 w2];

        else
            grain      = grain_sou.* [w2 w2];
        end

        % =====
        DAFx_out(pin+1:pin+s_win,:) = DAFx_out(pin+1:pin+s_win,:)
+ grain;
        pin          = pin + n1;
    end

    %----- listening and saving the output -----
    % DAFx_in = DAFx_in(s_win+1:s_win+L);

    DAFx_out = DAFx_out(s_win+1:length(DAFx_out),:) /
max(abs(DAFx_out(:)));
    %soundsc(DAFx_out, SR);
    DAFx_out_norm = r * DAFx_out/max(abs(DAFx_out(:))); % scale
for wav output
    %wavwrite(DAFx_out_norm, SR, './Results/any.wav')

end

```

Appendix B

Get words, syllables and phonemes Code

```
function [nwords, nofsyllables, nphonemes, comp_word,
complete_text_words,text_syllables,thdline] =
getphonemes_auto (transcription)

% Get Info
%-----Init-----%
nwords=1;
nphonemes=0;
nsyllables=0;
temp_n_syllables=0;
%-----To find words-----%

fid = fopen(transcription,'r'); % Open text file
b=fread(fid, '*char');
b=b';

for i=1:length(b) %Find ind for first and second line
indfands=strfind(b, '/');
sile=strfind(b, 'Sil'); % Find silences
end

% Points in Line 1 and Line 2

Line1=[indfands(1),indfands(2)-1];
Line2= [sile(1)+4,sile(2)-2];
Line2_v= [sile(1)+4:sile(2)-2];
Line3= [sile(3)+4,sile(4)-2];
Line3_v= [sile(3)+4:sile(4)-2];

%-----To locate words and
syllables-----%

word_start=strfind(b(Line2(1):Line2(2)), '['); %Find word
start
word_end=strfind(b(Line2(1):Line2(2)), ']'); %Find word end
nwords=length(word_start); %Number of words
----->One Data

%Clustering words vector
division = [];
text_syllables=[];
fidi=fopen('Info_trans.txt', 'w'); % Open Info File
%format= '%s,%f,%s\n';
%format='%s,%f,';

for j=1:nwords %j=1:nwords

    format = [];
    format='%s,%f,';
```

```

    words_values(j,:)=[word_start(j),word_end(j)]; %Start
and end of each word
    text=b(Line2_v(word_start(j)):Line2_v(word_end(j)));
    text_words{j,:}=text; %Words Cell

    word_1 {j} = text; % These are the words

    %Find Syllables%

    syll_sep=strfind(text_words, '.');

    if isempty(syll_sep{j})
        text_syllables = [text_syllables;
text_words(j,:)];
        length(syll_sep)
        format=[format, '%s, \n'];
        fprintf(fidi, format,
word_1{j},length(syll_sep),word_1{j})

    else %if there are syllables

        length(syll_sep); %Number of syllables separations
        boundaries= [0 syll_sep{j} length(text_words{j})
+1]; %Defines where separations are
        div_char=text_words{j};
        format=[format, '%s, \n'];
        for k =1:length(boundaries)-1
            %format=[format, '%s, \n'];
            text_syllables = [text_syllables;
mat2cell(div_char(boundaries(k)+1:boundaries(k+1)-1))];
            %% Atenci'on aca
            %% Atenci'on aca
            fprintf(fidi, format, word_1{j},length(syll_sep),
div_char(boundaries(k)+1:boundaries(k+1)-1))

            text_syllables_2=text_syllables';
        end

        temp_n_syllables= length(text_syllables);

    end

end

fclose('all')

any_variable=0;

for i=1:nwords

    word_1_info{i}=length(syll_sep{i}); %Number of
separations in each word
    comp_word{i}=word_1_info{i}+1; %Number of Syllables in
each word

end

%Is the syllable accentuated

```

```

complete_text_words=text_words;
%-----
---> Second Data
% disp ('These are the words in the text:')
% text_words

%-----Removing brackets from
syllables-----%
text_syllable_nb=strrep(text_syllables,[' ','']);
text_syllable_nb=strrep(text_syllable_nb,']','');

% %-----Display Results-----%
% disp ('These are the words in the text:')
% text_words
% disp ('These are the syllables:')
% text_syllable %Final syllables cell
% disp ('Number of words:')
% nwords
% disp ('Number of syllables:')
nofsyllables=length(text_syllables);

%-----To find phonetic
families/classes-----%
thdline=b(Line3_v); % Reads phonemes line
nphonemes=length(thdline);
% disp ('Number of phonemes:')
% length(thdline)
%---monophthongs---%
[monopcounter]=monophthongscounter(thdline);
[diphcounter]=diphthongscounter(thdline);
[triphcounter]=triphthongscounter(thdline);
vowelstotal= monopcounter+diphcounter+triphcounter;
[semvowcounter]=semivowcounter(thdline);
[nascounter]=nasalscounter(thdline);
[unvoifriccounter]=unvoicedfricatives(thdline);
[voicedfri_counter]=voicedfricounter(thdline);
[whispcounter]=whispercounter(thdline);
[voicaffriccounter]=VoicedAffricates(thdline);
[liquids_counter]=liquidscounter(thdline);
[unvoiplosivescounter]=unvoicedplosivescounter(thdline);
[voiplosivescounter]=voicedplosivescounter(thdline);

end

```